

“Importance of the use of EPS contracts in Uzbekistan”

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Abstract: *In this article, in addition to studying the type of eps contract typical of "Fidich" contracts, which are widely used in construction works, we will study the concepts of this contract, its features, types, and at the same time, the importance of knowing how to apply it in the territory of Uzbekistan. First of all, it will be briefly mentioned about the advantage of the contract in several foreign countries where the main experience EPS contract is in force.*

Keywords: *EPS contract, project, professional, infrastructure, budget system, production, tax benefits, contractor, customers.*

The Minister of Justice of Uzbekistan, Ruslanbek Davletov, in his speech at the 23rd plenary session of the Senate on February 4, 2023, emphasized the need to move to concluding contracts according to the standards of the FIDIC International Federation of Consulting Engineers of Uzbekistan. Involved in projects financed by international organizations for professionals, lawyers, employees of international banks and individual representatives of engineering and consulting companies, as well as for employees of project implementation groups, the concept of "FIDIC" should be considered a tool for everyday work. But it must be admitted that the acronym "FIDIC" in a broad sense remains ambiguous. With the help of experts, we try to find out what FIDIC standards can give to the domestic engineering market.

The International Federation of Consulting Engineers, or FIDIC for short, is the global representative body of national associations of consulting engineers, representing more than 100 engineering professionals and more than 40,000 firms. FIDIC standardizes contracts widely used in the global construction and engineering industry, primarily for high-cost international construction projects sanctioned by many multilateral development banks.

With the exception of projects financed from the budgets of the Ministry of Construction of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as from loans under the guaranty of the Government of the Republic of Uzbekistan, projects are "handover ready" for use (Engineering Procurement Construction) (hereinafter - EPC-contractors) in the "fast-track" style. (simultaneous design, procurement and construction works) to contractors, including foreign contractors, without obtaining relevant licenses or permits in the field of construction, on quality implementation of projects has the right to issue a one-time permit under the condition that full responsibility is placed on the EPC-contractors.

The fact that the parties to the EPS contract are not only Uzbeks, but also that one party is a foreigner creates many conveniences. Because our republic has a number of benefits in this regard. First of all, if the international agreement of the Republic of Uzbekistan stipulates different rules than those stipulated by the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rules of the international agreement shall be applied. Thus, it is worth noting that the benefits applied to enterprises with the participation of foreign investment are the following benefits in the taxation of legal entities:

1. New construction, reconstruction of buildings and structures used for production needs, as well as funds directed to the expansion of the main production in the form of repayment of loans received for these purposes;

2. Funds allocated for modernization of production, technical and technological re-equipment, purchase of new technological equipment, repayment of loans given for these purposes, compensation of the value of the leased object.

In addition, our state provides income tax, VAT benefits for manufactured and sold products, land tax, tax benefits for the use of water resources, tax benefits for the use of underground resources, property tax benefits, benefits for turnover tax payers, customs benefits are set for their payments, which gives some relief to the parties.

It appears that EPS is an international form of contract used in the field of construction and engineering. If we look at the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, a similar contract attracts attention. In the contract contract, as well as in the EPS contract, according to the customer's project, the general contractor undertakes all the work and completes the work. But the EPS contract is divided into EPSM, EPSI contract types and it is used on a wider scale unlike the contract contract.

The EPS contractor performs the main part of the investment and construction project work at a fixed price and assumes all the risks of its implementation from the moment of design to the handover of the finished object to the customer. EPS contracts are an important part of agreements in the building and construction industry today. This is because, as we mentioned above, the EPS agreement between the parties assigns responsibility for the design and construction of the entire facility to a single party, the general contractor. An EPS contractor often assigns a project schedule to a developer who can work immediately. Any developer capable of performing the work to be performed on the project may be appointed by the general

contractor as a subcontractor to the general contractor. In this case, the general contractor does not have to report this to the customer. Because all responsibility for the EPS contract concluded between the customer and the general contractor is assigned to the general contractor.

Like all contracts, the EPS contract has its advantages and disadvantages. So, we can see that this agreement can be applied in the country of Uzbekistan in the following aspects of flexibility:

Minimal financial and negative legal consequences;

- Selection of all "services" from one executor (contractor);
- Non-interference of the customer in the project process;
- There are minimum hiring and construction costs.

At the same time, there is an EPSM type of EPS contract, which includes the following advantages:

- The total cost of the project is 5-10% lower than usual;
- Mergers of customer parties;
- Greater than usual customer control over the project;
- Such as proportionality in financing.

The contract does not only have its advantages, but it also has its own disadvantages, which can be seen mainly in the fact that it places more responsibility on the contractor. Before that, it is necessary to dwell on the differences between the types of EPS contracts. Therefore, in order to decide whether to start the construction of each facility of their enterprise, the customers will first have to choose the type of contract that is proportionate to them and can look after their interests at the highest level. The selection is made on the basis of legal considerations and price level.

It is known that many measures have been implemented in order to introduce modern mechanisms of implementation of investment and infrastructure projects, to agree and approve project-estimate documents and to simplify the procedure for carrying out construction and assembly works, as well as to strengthen the role and responsibility of contractors in capital construction. At the same time, there are many laws on the implementation of holding projects, according to which the management of a specific project on the implementation of the EPS/M-contract in the organizational structure of the holding company cannot be closed only within the framework of the parent company. Undoubtedly, the most effective way to implement the project is to create an interactive organizational structure according to the corporate quality management system, which allows not only to respond flexibly to the specifics of each project, but also to describe and place standard business processes and procedures between the elements of the organizational structure.

The basic organizational structure for the implementation of the EPS/M contract allows you to create the necessary rules and guidelines, the general system, even taking into account the adjustments for the individuality of projects, quality management. At the same time, this structure includes management accounting and control of the integration of all companies within the holding on the basis of a single information system, namely the project control department and information technology.

The idea is simple, one contractor will be engaged for everything from engineering design to procurement of materials and equipment, as well as direct construction. Therefore, only one service provider needs to be monitored. Considering the fact that there are many different works in the construction of facilities in new mines, the correct location of the transmission line plays a key role

in the construction of contracts, even in simple matters, in order to synchronize the actions of contractors. An integral part of the EPS contract package is the contract strategy, in which the implementation of each EPS project is determined by specific technological contracts with planned implementation dates. In addition, it is advisable to enter into a project management consulting contract for contract support services when drawing up an EPS contract. Within its framework, the compatibility of the "internal" contracts of the contract with each other is controlled and the acceptance of certain works is controlled. Such contracts are very important for the supply of complex equipment that can be manufactured anywhere in the world is important. It's all about choosing the executor of the EPS contract.

Therefore, the EPS contractor, in accordance with the contract, undertakes to provide the customer with services for the design of the facility, purchase of equipment and construction. Under this form of contracting, project implementation processes are largely under the control of the contractor and provide little direct control of the client. Under the EPS contract, the contractor is entitled to negotiate all contracts directly with other contractors. This in itself plays a big role in increasing productivity.

According to Ukrainian legislation, EPSM (Engineering, Supply and Construction Management-Design, Procurement and Construction Management) EPSM contractor undertakes to provide management (process management) services for design, procurement and construction to the customer in accordance with the contract. In this case, the customer personally agrees with the contractors on the order of all the processes of design, purchase and construction through individual contracts. These processes (design, procurement, construction) are managed by the general contractor EPSM on behalf of the customer.

Thus, EPS and EPSM contracts are the most common contract types in the international construction industry. Among the projects, the sponsor and the client choose the one that is most convenient for them, depending on the level of risk, cost-effectiveness and the scope of the mandate.

In conclusion, it should be noted that EPS/M holding does not have to be clearly expressed in life, some functions may intersect and complement each other in holding companies. In addition, the trend of reforming construction holdings is rapidly showing this direction of development, so it is better for the management of corporations not to waste time.

The practice of concluding EPS contracts is widespread abroad. For example, it is quite popular in the Middle East, first of all, of course, in rich countries. United Arab Emirates, Kuwait, Qatar, business prefer to enter into a large contract with a contractor who will build the enterprise under this new contract and take all the problems and risks.

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